

THEORETICAL BASICS OF TECHNOLOGICAL METHODS IN THE PROCESS OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE EDUCATION

Shakhlo Khakimovna Kharatova

Associate Professor of Tashkent State Transport University

ORCID identifier: 0000-0002-6535-0197

Email: SHAHLO-70@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7691727>

Abstract: This article, methodological recommendations on the use of the case study method for bilingual teaching of English and optional classes are presented based on scientific principles.

Key words: rotate through angle, terminal speed, problem situations (case studies).

New lexical information is successful if it is personally relevant to learners. Therefore, regardless of the form of conducting classes (for example, lectures, practice, laboratory, elective courses, classes with masters), it is not appropriate to present new terms to students in a ready form, because in this case, students are active with terms they don't work. On the other hand, active research in the field of linguistics encourages the reconstruction and deepening of the existing knowledge structure.

In many cases, phrases have signs of a syntactically and semantically integrated unit, one of its components is chosen according to meaning, and the choice of the second depends on the choice of the first and is determined by tradition. For example, the phrase "rotate through angle" corresponds to the phrase "rotate through angle". In the course of practical training, fixed phrases on the subject, found collocations should fill the subject's individual vocabulary.

Among the types of educational activities in optional classes, we include texts and parts of texts, referring and referring to new concepts, denotations, terms, appropriate subject-predicate relations, answers to questions, as well as exercises for finding synonyms. we introduce informative reading. After completing the analysis of new words (language form), it is necessary to return to the content analysis for active use of the new vocabulary, the best tool of which is to solve a set of problematic communicative-cognitive tasks.

In the following examples, the concept of terminal speed is presented in the text as a statement of the task and is actively used in the process of solving it.

Problem 1. A raindrop with radius 1.5 mm falls from a cloud that is at height 1200 m above the ground. The drag coefficient C for the drop is 0.6. Assume that the drop is spherical throughout its fall. The density of water is 1000 kg/m³, and the density of air is 1.2 kg/m³. (a) What is the terminal speed of the drop? (b) What would be the drop's speed just before impact if there were no drag force?

Problem 2. The terminal speed of a sky diver is 160 km/h in the spread-eagle position and 310 km/h in the nosedive position. Assuming that the diver's drag coefficient C does not change from one position to the other, find the ratio of the effective cross-sectional area A in the slower position to that in the faster position.

The integrated lessons conducted with students of the graduate course aim to teach a professional foreign language, so language practice takes the leading place, and the content part plays an auxiliary role, creating a basis for language practice.

The implementation of the stated goal of teaching the students of the graduate course allows to attract additional tools for bilingual teaching of the subject and the appropriate methods and methods for optional classes, as well as for the formation of professional vocabulary in two languages. It is not intended to obtain a normative result of learning the content of the material in the form of checking the knowledge available in the special science program. This causes variability of the temporary resources of educational material and types of educational activities.

We believe that problematic situations (case studies) with modeling elements of professional activity have an important potential in achieving the activity of graduate students, including reflection in their minds, working with professional lexical units. Such technology is very suitable for working with future managers, for example, graduate students in the field of "technosphere security".

For example, based on relevant materials posted on the website of the government organization for ensuring labor protection, Health and Safety Executive - the UK national independent watchdog for work-related health, safety and illness.[1] Students of the graduate course are offered sample situations to determine measures to ensure the safety of employees in small enterprises. Preliminary information (setting the scene) for dry cleaners is determined: location of the enterprise, type of building (number of floors of the building, year of construction, location of equipment, availability of stairs), number of employees. Based on the analysis of the company's work, at the first stage, both participants of the discussion of the problem model situation make a list of risks that employees may face during the hours allocated for independent work. The first assumptions can be as follows.

List of hazards

1. Use of chlorinated solvents, e.g. perchloroethylene.
2. Use of chemicals for spot-cleaning.
3. Musculoskeletal injuries.
4. Slips and trips.
5. Violence and threatening behavior.
6. Working at height (eg. changing light bulbs).
7. Electrical (eg. faulty building wiring or faulty electrical appliances).
8. Pressure vessels.
9. Fire (eg. smoking, faulty electrics, arson).
10. Asbestos.

In the audience, each participant presents his list of potential hazards and explains in English how each of the listed types can harm the health of workers. Class work is done in pairs, students make a common list as a result of complementing each other. At the next stage, students will be given written instructions on how to take measures to reduce health risks. The results of the research will be presented in the audience in English.

Summary. The purpose and task of conducting a lesson in the form of a discussion of a problem situation is to enable the participants to learn the definitions of special terms together with semantic relations.

Examples of common terms for basic relationships in science:

Table 1.

Type of hazard	Who might be harmed and how?	What actions are necessary to prevent it?
Working at height (e.g. changing light bulbs)	Staff risk injuries such as bruising or fractures from falls any height.	Strong stepladder in good condition provided and staff are trained to use it safely.
Slips and trips	Staff/customers risk injuries such as fractures/bruises, if they trip over objects or slip on slippages	Staff clean up spillages promptly and, where necessary, use 'wet floor' signs. Stairs well lit and in good condition. Door mats put at entrance in wet weather

New terms and concepts can be formed by adding cause, place, time, shape, structure, physical properties, purpose and other parameters to previously known terms.

REFERENCES:

1. Kharatova, S. (2022, November). THE ROLE OF INTEGRATED EDUCATION IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. In *Международная конференция академических наук* (Vol. 1, No. 31, pp. 4-6).
2. Kharatova, S., & Khusanova, I. (2022). PROBLEMS OF PLANNING ENGLISH LESSONS. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 1(6), 214-217.
3. Kharatova, S. (2022). PERSONAL QUALITIES AND JOBS. *Current approaches and new research in modern sciences*, 1(5), 51-55.
4. Kharatova, S. (2022). MODERN METHODS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 1(6), 31-34.
5. Kharatova, S. (2022). METHODS OF INDEPENDENT LEARNING ENGLISH. BEST ENGLISH LEARNING TECHNIQUE. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 1(16), 49-52.
6. Kharatova, S. K. (2022). Concept of Language and Speech. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 2(4), 115-117.
7. Ахматова, Х. Ш. (2017). Концептуальные основы разработки технологий воспитания средствами иностранного языка в техническом вузе. *Современные инновации*, (3 (17)), 41-42.
8. Kharatova, S. (2022, November). THE ROLE OF INTEGRATED EDUCATION IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. In *Международная конференция академических наук* (Vol. 1, No. 31, pp. 4-6).
9. Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 713-718.
10. Харатова, Ш. Х., & Садикова, М. Б. (2020). Эффективные способы изучения английского языка. *Academy*, (2 (53)), 33-35.
11. Kharatova, S. K. (2021). TENDENCIES OF DEVELOPMENT OF DISTANCE EDUCATION IN GLOBAL TRANSFORMATION. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(10), 353-362.

12. Kharatova, S. (2022). THE ROLE OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE PROJECTS AND TECHNOLOGIES. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 2(10), 128-130.
13. Kharatova, S. K. Goals And Tasks Of English Language Teaching. *International Bulletin Of Engineering And Technology*, 2(9).
14. Kharatova, S. K. (2021). TEACH ENGLISH FOR SPESIFIC PURPOSES. *THEORETICAL AND APPLIED SCIENCE*, 11, 30.
15. Kharatova, S. (2022). TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF LANGUAGE SKILLS IN ENGLISH CLASSES. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 1(6), 20-24.
16. Kharatova, S. (2022). METHODS OF INDEPENDENT LEARNING ENGLISH. BEST ENGLISH LEARNING TECHNIQUE. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 1(16), 49-52.
17. Kharatova, S. K. (2022). Concept of Language and Speech. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 2(4), 115-117.
18. Kharatova, S. K. (2022). COMMUNICATIVE EXERCISES IN TEACHING GRAMMAR CHARACTERISTICS OF ENGLISH VERBS. *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL)*, 3(2), 50-53.
19. Kharatova, S. K. (2022). Characteristics of the pedagogical process system. *Science and Education*, 3(6), 681-686.
20. Kharatova, S. (2021). INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH. *Экономика и социум*, (3-1), 132-134.
21. Alidjanovna, T. M., Khakimovna, K. S., Tulaboevna, T. G., Shukurovna, A. K., & Xafizovich, U. K. (2021). Lingu-Didactical Basis of Teaching English Learning Vocabulary to the First-Year Uzbek Audience Students. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 415-429.
22. Kharatova, S. K. (2021). STRATEGIC ISSUES OF IMPROVING SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(11), 313-320.
23. Kharatova, S. K. (2021). PROBLEMS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING AND ITS SOLUTION. *Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире*, (4-8), 60-62.
24. Kharatova, S. K. (2021). The importance of foreign language teaching in higher education institutions. *Science and Education*, 2(5), 751-756.
25. Allanazarova, M., Tashtemirova, M., Xaratova, S., Sadiqova, M., & Jalilova, M. (2020). Verbalization of concept "water and fire" in English linguoculturology. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(2), 382-386.
26. Харатова, Ш. Х. (2019). ИННОВАЦИОННО–ОРИЕНТИРОВАННОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ КАК ФАКТОР СОВЕРШЕНСТВАВОНИЯ ОПЕРЕЖАЮЩЕГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ВУЗА НА СОВРЕМЕННОМ ЭТАПЕ. In *Университетский комплекс как региональный центр образования, науки и культуры* (pp. 4117-4120).
27. Харатова, Ш. Х. (2019). ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫЙ ПРОЦЕСС В ОБУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА (АНГЛИЙСКИЙ) В НЕЛИНГИСТИЧЕСКИХ ИНСТИТУТАХ.

In Университетский комплекс как региональный центр образования, науки и культуры (pp. 2585-2588).

28. Расулова, З. Х. (2017). Эффективность коммуникативных и компьютерных технологий в изучении иностранных языков. *Современные инновации*, (3 (17)), 45-47.
29. Харатова, Ш. Х. (2017). Явление интерференции родного и русского языков при контакте с иностранным языком. *Современные инновации*, (3 (17)), 39-41.
30. Kharatova, S. (2022). TEACHING METHODOLOGY AND TECHNOLOGY IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSONS. *Current approaches and new research in modern sciences*, 1(7), 20-24.
31. Харатова, Ш. Х., Назарова, Н. Ж., Абдукаримова, Г. Б., Рахимова, М. И., & Темирова, С. В. (2022). ВОЯГА ЕТМАГАН ЎСМИРЛАР БИЛАН ИШЛАШДА ОИЛА, МАҲАЛЛА, МАКТАБ ҲАМКОРЛИГИ МАСАЛАЛАРИ. *Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 11, 102-110.
32. Kh, I. T. (2021). Musical currents and the formation of Russian classical music. *Вестник магистратуры*, (5-1 (116)), 7-8.
33. Ismailov, T. K. (2021). Characteristics Of Khorezm Doston Art. *Экономика и социум*, (3-1), 96-98.
34. Ismailov, T. K. (2021). The Importance Of Russian Classical Composers In Classes Of Music Culture. *Экономика и социум*, (1-1), 93-95.
35. Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2021). Musiqa madaniyati darslarida rus kompozitorlari ijodi orqali o'quvchilarning estetik didini rivojlantirish. *Science and Education*, 2(4), 336-340.
36. Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 713-718.
37. Xushnudbek o'g'li, I. T. (2021). Formation of student aesthetic competition by teaching the works of Russian classic composers in music culture classes. *Молодой ученый*, 17, 359.
38. Xushnudbek o'g'li, I. T. (2022). PI CHAKOVSKIY ASARLARI MAZMUNINING UMUMNAZARIY-TARIXIY JARAYONLARI. *Science and Education*, (3).
39. Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). PI CHAYKOVSKIY "YIL FASLLARI" ASARINING MAZMUN-MOHİYATI BILAN TANISHISH. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(3), 1460-1475.
40. Ismailov, T. (2022). THE LIGHT FROM THE SHOVIOT OR ABOUT THE SHRINE OF HIS HOLINESS" YUSUF KHAMADONI". *Models and methods in modern science*, 1(17), 12-15.
41. Ismailov, T. (2022, November). THE FORT THAT SPEAKS FROM THE PAST. In *Международная конференция академических наук* (Vol. 1, No. 31, pp. 18-22).
42. Xushnudebk o'g'li, I. T. (2022). PI CHAYKOVSKIY "YIL FASLLARI" ASARINING MAZMUN-MOHİYATI BILAN TANISHISH.
43. Ismailov, T., & Yusupova, M. (2022). Insonga psixologik ta'sir ko'rsatish turlari va texnikasi. *Science and Education*, 3(6), 913-920.

44. Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L., & Ibragimov, B. M. (2022). Magistratura stajirovkasi hisoboti. *Science and Education*, 3(4), 738-740.
45. Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). PI Chaykovskiy asarlari mazmunining umumnazariy-tarixiy jarayonlari. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 762-772.
46. Kharatova, S. K. (2021). STRATEGIC ISSUES OF IMPROVING SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(11), 313-320.
47. Ismailov, T., & Karimova, D. (2021). FORMATION OF STUDENT AESTHETIC COMPETITION BY TEACHING THE WORKS OF RUSSIAN CLASSIC COMPOSERS IN MUSIC CULTURE CLASSES. *Интернаука*, (15-3), 59-60.